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Khurramov Anvar Khudayshukurovich
Tashkent University of Economics and Technologies
khurramovanvar907@gmail.com

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ENHANCING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTRUCTORS DURING DISTANCE EDUCATION

Abstract. This article examines the development of information and communication skills among university educators through the use of distance learning tools. With increasing demands for higher professional education standards, there is a shift from the traditional "education for life" model to a more dynamic "lifelong learning" approach. This change drives trends such as continuity, mass participation, foundational knowledge, personalization, humanization, and a competency-based framework.

Key words: information and communication competence, distance learning, level of training, teacher, university, vocational education, new technologies.

Хуррамов Анвар Худайшукурович
Ташкентский Университет Экономики и Технологий

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается развитие информационно-коммуникационных навыков у преподавателей университетов с использованием инструментов дистанционного обучения. С ростом требований к стандартам профессионального образования возникает необходимость перехода от традиционной модели «образование для жизни» к более динамичной концепции «образование в течение всей жизни». Это изменение стимулирует тенденции в современном образовании, такие как непрерывность, массовое участие, фундаментальные знания, персонализация, гуманизация и компетентностный подход.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационная компетентность, дистанционное обучение, уровень подготовки, преподаватель, университет, профессиональное образование, новые технологии.

Xurramov Anvar Xudayshukurovich
Toshkent Iqtisodiyot va Texnologiyalar Universiteti

OLIV TA'LIM O'QITUVCHILARINING MASOFAVIY TA'LIM DAVRIDAGI AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA KO'NIKALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola universitet o'qituvchilarining axborot-kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarini masofaviy o'qitish vositalari orqali rivojlantirishni o'rganadi. Kasbiy ta'limning yuqori standartlariga bo'lgan talablarning ortishi bilan, an'anaviy "hayot uchun ta'lim" modelidan "umrbod ta'lim"ga o'tish zarurati tug'ilmoqda. Ushbu o'zgarish uzluksizlik, ommaviy qatnashish, asosiy bilimlar, shaxsiylashtirish, insonparvarlik va kompetensiyaga asoslangan yondashuv kabi zamonaviy ta'limdagi tendensiyalarga turtki beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot-kommunikatsiya kompetensiyasi, masofaviy ta'lim, tayyorgarlik darajasi, o'qituvchi, universitet, kasbiy ta'lim, yangi texnologiyalar.

Introduction.

The evolving demands for specialist training and individual qualities have prompted reforms in Uzbekistan's education system. Efforts are being made to consolidate information and educational resources and to integrate information and communication technologies

into the educational process. This is further supported by the development of infrastructures that offer free access to educational resources to a broad population, irrespective of their location[1].

Recent reforms in Uzbekistan's education sector have highlighted key areas for development. It has become

clear that a shift from the traditional “education for life” model to a more dynamic “education throughout life” approach is necessary. Higher education is now viewed as a crucial driver of social and economic advancement. As American educator R. Hutchinson suggests, the ultimate aim of education is to enhance human potential, reflecting the recognition that the true value and main asset of modern society is an individual capable of acquiring new knowledge and making innovative decisions.

This shift in educational paradigm brings to light major trends in modern education: continuity, mass accessibility, foundational knowledge, personalization, humanization, and a focus on competencies. New technological capabilities and innovations enable the organization of the educational process at a higher level, vastly expanding the methods and forms of its delivery. Distance learning is one such method. According to Andreev A.A., Polat E.S., and Khutorsky A.B., distance learning involves interactions between teachers and students, as well as between students themselves, occurring remotely through information and communication technologies, rather than face-to-face[2,3].

Integrating distance learning tools into traditional university settings requires a certain level of information and communication competence from educators. Teachers with traditional training may struggle to implement distance learning tools immediately due to different technologies, new communication methods, and modern management techniques, which require specific qualifications. Thus, developing a level of competence in information and communication technologies is essential for teachers to effectively incorporate these tools into their teaching processes.

Literature Review. The literature review focuses on analyzing existing studies and resources related to the modernization of education, the integration of information and communication technologies (ICT), and global trends in distance learning. The key points include: The critical role of ICT in enhancing educational processes. Scholars such as Andreev A.A., Polat E.S., and Khutorsky A.B. emphasize the advantages of distance learning technologies, which enable interaction between teachers and students without physical presence[4].

Inspired by R. Hutchinson's idea that "the primary goal of education is to enhance human potential," there is a growing emphasis on transitioning from the traditional "education for life" model to "education throughout life." The necessity of continuous learning and personalized education to meet modern demands[5].

Development of teacher competencies in ICT and the creation of methodological tools for effective teaching in a distance learning environment. Studies highlight the importance of platforms like Moodle in supporting pedagogical tasks.

Methods to integrate distance learning with traditional teaching. International experiences, such as projects in Russia and the U.S., demonstrate the successful adoption of ICT in education.

The literature review concludes that establishing specific pedagogical conditions to enhance remote interaction between teachers and students is essential for successfully implementing modern educational technologies.

Research Methodology. The aim of this research is to identify and implement pedagogical conditions for developing teachers' information and communication competence in a distance learning environment and to provide practical recommendations for improving educational processes. The research methodology includes the following stages: Examination of scientific articles, books, and international research to identify challenges and trends in distance learning[6].

Development of theoretical models to define the pedagogical conditions necessary for integrating ICT into education.

Analysis of the distance learning process and evaluation of its outcomes.

Collecting feedback from teachers and students to understand their experiences and needs in using distance learning tools.

Designing and conducting experiments to implement and evaluate the proposed pedagogical conditions in real educational settings.

Application of Moodle as the primary tool for creating training modules, facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration, and ensuring accessibility of educational materials[7].

This methodology ensures a comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges of integrating distance learning technologies and enhancing the competence of educators in using ICT effectively[8].

Discussion and results.

Enhancing teachers information and communication competence within a distance learning support environment aims to elevate the quality of addressing pedagogical challenges through the integration of advanced information technologies into the educational process. As discussed earlier, the effectiveness of developing this competence in a distance learning environment largely hinges on the implementation of specific pedagogical conditions (see Fig. 1).

Organizational conditions set the standards for structuring a distributed environment and its physical setup. The first chapter examined these organizational requirements, while the second chapter detailed their physical implementation. Successful adherence to these organizational conditions necessitates a thorough evaluation of appropriate software products for use in the environment.

Methodological conditions involve outlining the tools available within the educational environment, providing guidance for teachers on how to utilize these tools, and establishing methods for interdisciplinary interaction within the environment. This includes detailing procedures for creating course elements, evaluating test tasks, and assessing the effectiveness of the educational process.

Motivational conditions are designed to boost both teachers' and students' enthusiasm and readiness to engage with the distance learning support environment. They also encourage teachers' professional growth, aiming to elevate their teaching to a higher level of quality.

Fig.1. Implementation of appropriate pedagogical conditions for the development of information and communication competence of teachers in a distance learning support environment

In selecting software for deploying training modules in a distance learning support environment, Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) was chosen due to its global popularity. Moodle offers a range of features for delivering educational and methodological content, assessing knowledge, tracking progress, and facilitating both individual and group activities.

The development of teachers' formative and communicative competence in a distance learning support setting involves preparing to use the pedagogical tools offered by this software at various levels of competence. The methodological recommendations include detailed descriptions of the educational tools available in the environment, guidance for teachers on utilizing these tools, and strategies for interdisciplinary collaboration. It also covers procedures for designing course components, evaluating test tasks, and measuring the effectiveness of the educational process. The aim of these preparations is to enhance the educational process's effectiveness and elevate it to a new level through the integration of advanced information technologies.

The preparation process is structured into five interconnected stages:

Stage I: Introduces teachers to the underlying principles, interface, and basic interactions with the tools

provided by Moodle. It involves lectures to engage teachers with these tools, demonstrates how to combine different teaching methods, and explores the organization of interdisciplinary communication. Special focus is given to the creation of meta-courses and meta-portals, which facilitate collaborative work on educational materials and various methods of organizing such interactions.

Stage II: Develops teachers' abilities to ensure that educational materials are consistently available to students and integrates this accessibility with traditional teaching methods.

Stage III: Equips teachers with skills to employ active teaching methods such as chats, forums, and seminars, using the technological resources provided by the environment.

Stage IV: Teaches teachers how to create question banks and design multi-level tests, implementing effective feedback mechanisms. This stage helps teachers adapt educational materials based on students' cognitive abilities, efficiently assess a large number of students, and build a comprehensive assessment system. The tools available allow for the generation of highly reliable tests.

Stage V: Involves mastering elements of the environment that support programmed training. This stage enables teachers to adapt educational materials according to student responses and develop mixed learning models (linear, concentric, spiral). Combining these with traditional methods enhances the volume of information delivered and transforms the lesson delivery process. Teachers are also introduced to the latest features of the environment.

Conclusion.

By shifting traditional teachers toward an effective blend of classical and distance learning technologies, the educational process can be greatly enhanced. The proposed system for boosting teachers' information and communication competence in the distance learning support environment is designed to achieve optimal results quickly and to boost teachers' motivation to utilize modern technologies in their teaching.

Information competence for higher education teachers is a comprehensive, multi-faceted, and professionally important quality. It is demonstrated through the ability to manage various types of information within teaching activities, fulfilling roles related to information processing, orientation, mobilization, organization, construction, communication, and development.

Information competence in higher education teachers is regarded from several perspectives: as a valuable attribute (state, public, social, personal) that is a significant qualitative factor for advancing the educational space by cultivating a modern, information-capable teacher; as a system for structuring knowledge and skills, reflected in the ability to handle different types of information in teaching; and as a product of the individual's internal development, particularly in understanding their role and self-evaluating their information activities within the framework of continuing professional education.

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